

GSV and RSV carriers in BPH caught in a high-beam light trap, IRRI, 1983–84.

Collection dates	BPH tested no.	GSV carrier		RSV carrier		Collection dates	BPH tested no.	GSV carrier		RSV carrier	
		no.	%	no.	%			no.	%	no.	%
28 Jan-6 Feb	5	0	—	1	20.0	5-14 Sep	199	1	0.5	2	1.0
7-16 Feb	0	—	—	—	—	15-24 Sep	145	0	—	0	—
17-26 Feb	13	1	7.7	2	15.4	25 Sep-4 Oct	55	0	—	0	—
27 Feb-8 Mar	67	8	11.9	13	19.4	5-14 Oct	43	0	—	0	—
9-18 Mar	33	1	3.0	0	—	15-24 Oct	77	1	1.3	0	—
19-28 Mar	207	0	—	0	—	25 Oct-3 Nov	92	0	—	0	—
29 Mar-7 Apr	271	9	3.3	34	12.5	4-13 Nov	4	1	25.0	0	—
8-17 Apr	134	0	—	3	2.2	14-23 Nov	109	0	—	0	—
18-27 Apr	139	0	—	4	2.9	24 Nov-3 Dec	45	0	—	1	2.2
28 Apr-7 May	74	1	1.4	2	2.7	4-13 Dec	0	—	—	—	—
8-17 May	50	2	3.3	1	1.7	14-23 Dec	0	—	—	—	—
18-27 May	65	1	1.5	3	4.6	24 Dec-3 Jan 1984	0	—	—	—	—
28 May-6 Jun	27	0	—	3	11.1	4-13 Jan	2	—	—	—	—
7-16 Jun	99	3	3.0	6	6.1	14-23 Jan	2	—	—	—	—
17-26 Jun	91	1	1.1	3	3.3	24 Jan-2 Feb	0	—	—	—	—
27 Jun-6 Jul	108	0	—	4	3.7	3-12 Feb	8	—	—	—	—
7-16 Jul	41	0	—	2	4.9	13-22 Feb	3	—	—	—	—
17-26 Jul	0	—	—	—	—	23 Feb-3 Mar	2	—	—	—	—
27 Jul-5 Aug	0	—	—	—	—	4-13 Mar	147	1	0.7	3	2.0
6-15 Aug	0	—	—	—	—	14-23 Mar	431	21	4.9	4	0.9
16-25 Aug	339	3	0.9	7	2.1	24 Mar-2 Apr	399	0	—	3	0.8
26 Aug-4 Sep	407	0	—	17	4.2	Total or average	3943	55	1.4	118	3.0

Percentage GSV and RSV carriers among migrating BPH from daily catches in a high-beam light trap at IRRI, 1983–84.

(pH 6.5) containing 0.15 M NaCl, 0.05% Tween 20, 0.02% NaN₃ and 2% polyvinylpyrrolidone. The homogenate was separately tested in ELISA using a purified immunoglobulin against GSV and RSV.

Of 3,943 BPH tested from Jan 1983 to Mar 1984, 1.4% carried GSV, 3.0% carried RSV, and 0.3% carried both viruses. Carriers per 10-d catch varied from 0.5 to 25.0% for GSV and from 0.8

to 20.0% for RSV (see table). Large numbers of BPH were trapped in Mar–Jun and Aug–Nov (see figure). *ℒ*

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Effect of foliar spray of macro- and micronutrients on sheath rot (ShR) incidence and rice grain yield

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ShR caused by *Sarocladium oryzae* is found in most rice-growing areas in

Tamil Nadu, causing yield losses up to 85%. To study the influence of foliar sprays of macro- and micronutrients on the development of ShR, a pot experiment using IR20 was conducted at the Paddy Experiment Station, Ambasamuduram, in 1984-85. The nutrients were sprayed twice at 30 and 55 d after transplanting (DT), and the plants were inoculated artificially with *S. oryzae* by inserting a single infected rice grain between the leaf sheath enclosing the panicle and the culm of a tiller. Inoculation was done at 65 DT and the disease incidence recorded 30 d after inoculation. Five tillers from each hill were selected at random and graded for disease incidence by SES and the percentage disease index was calculated.

ShR incidence was significantly lower in CaSO₄, ZnSO₄, and KCl treatments

Influence of foliar spray of macro- and micronutrients on ShR incidence and rice grain yield.^a

Nutrient	Concentration (%)	ShR disease index (%)	Grain yield (g/hill)
Urea	2.0	36.6 d	9.8 c
KCl	1.0	21.0 a	10.5 b
K ₂ SO ₄	1.0	25.8 b	10.2 bc
CaSO ₄	2.0	18.5 a	11.3 a
MgSO ₄	1.0	27.0 b	10.2 bc
ZnSO ₄	1.0	20.4 a	11.2 a
CuSO ₄	0.2	24.6 b	10.4 b
MnSO ₄	1.0	30.6 c	10.3 bc
FeSO ₄	1.0	32.4 c	10.0 c
Mixture (Zn: Cu: Mg: Fe: Mn = 10: 5: 2: 2: 1)	1.0	25.2 b	10.2 bc
Control	—	35.4 d	9.9 c

^a In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

(see table). CaSO₄ and ZnSO₄ gave the highest grain yield. Spraying with CuSO₄ also produced increased yield

and decreased ShR incidence. Foliar spray with urea had no effect on disease incidence or grain yield. *ℵ*

Pest Control and Management

INSECTS

Multiple allelism in brown planthopper (BPH) body color

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Adult BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* generally are brown. Occasionally, however, a few orange (O) and black (BL) variants appear in stock cultures maintained on rice plants. Crossbreeding these purified discrete color morphs and inbreeding their progenies have enabled the expression of intermediate color morphs that are dark brown (D-B), brownish orange (B-O), orange brown (O-B), blackish brown (BL-B), and brownish black (B-BL). To understand how BPH body color is inherited and to determine the influence of environment, we conducted breeding experiments involving at least two generations.

Parent insects came from pure breeding lines and were homozygous for body coloration. The figure summarizes

Hybridization scheme between brown (B), orange (O), and black (BL) BPH color morphs. F1 and F2 progenies comprising additional color morphs — dark brown (D-B), brownish orange (B-O), orange-brown (O-B), blackish brown (BL-B), and brownish black (B-BL) — are depicted within circles and rectangles. IRRI, 1985.

the results of the hybridization experiments. Inheritance of color morphism had the following trends:

1. The BPH gene for color morphism exists in three allelic forms, although any diploid male or